

FILIPINO TIKTOK INFLUENCERS AND PURCHASING BEHAVIOR OF YOUNG PROFESSIONALS

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Abstract

The traditional use of conventional media by businesses for audience targeting has shifted with the rise of influencer marketing, notably on platforms like TikTok, posing challenges in content adaptation and technological adaptation. Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory examines factors shaping purchasing behavior, particularly relevant for young professionals. A quantitative correlational study focused on young professionals engaging with TikTok and influenced by Filipino TikTok creators, revealing education level as a key determinant of purchasing behavior. Extended TikTok engagement positively correlates with increased purchasing likelihood. Filipino TikTok influencers significantly impact young professionals' purchasing decisions, emphasizing the need for tailored marketing strategies targeting this demographic. Recommendations were provided for effective influencer and digital marketing strategies targeting young professionals.

Keywords: *TikTok, Filipino TikTok Influencers, Influencer Marketing, Purchasing Behavior, Young Professionals.*

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Introduction

In the contemporary digital realm, the presence of 43.4 million Filipino adults on TikTok, highlighted by Inquirer.net (Baclig, 2023), emphasizes the platform's widespread influence. Among this user base, a significant demographic of young professionals aged 18 to 35 (United Nations, year) stands out, characterized by diverse characteristics such as gender, education, income, and occupation. Their engagement on TikTok goes beyond leisure; it serves as a crucial arena for marketers to tailor strategies that resonate with their lifestyles and preferences.

The shift from traditional media to influencer marketing, especially on TikTok, presents a challenge for businesses navigating technology and diverse demographics. Survey findings from the Statista Research Department (2023) reveal that 69 percent of Filipino respondents' base purchase decisions on influencer endorsements, highlighting the growing impact of this marketing approach. Understanding the complex factors influencing the purchasing behavior of young professionals becomes crucial, with influencers playing a pivotal role as trusted advisors (Santiago & Castelo, 2020). While Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) provides a theoretical framework, there's a gap in research on the specific influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on young professionals' choices. This study aims to bridge this gap, examining how SCT factors shape purchasing decisions under the influence of Filipino TikTok creators. Beyond academia, the research aims to guide businesses with effective influencer marketing and digital strategies tailored to this influential demographic.

Through an in-depth exploration of influencer marketing dynamics on TikTok among young professionals, the study seeks to uncover valuable insights. These insights not only contribute to scholarly discourse but also provide actionable recommendations for businesses to engage and retain the loyalty of this discerning and influential audience segment.

Statement of the Problem

The objective of this study was to explore the relationship between the personal, behavioral, and environmental factors, including Filipino TikTok influencers and their impact on the behavior of young professionals, specifically their purchasing behavior. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the profiles of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Gender;
 - b. Level of education;
 - c. Occupation;
 - d. Income;
 - e. Hours spent daily on TikTok; and
 - f. Product discoveries and purchases while browsing the application?
2. What is the level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals in terms of:
 - a. Environmental factors;
 - b. Personal factors; and

- c. Behavioral factors?
- 3. Is there a significant difference between the levels of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to profile variables?
- 4. Based on the findings of the study, what is the advocacy plan of the researchers?

Methodology

The study, titled "Filipino TikTok Influencers and Purchasing Behavior of Young Professionals," utilized a correlational research design with quantitative methods. It aimed to establish connections between environmental, behavioral, and personal factors and their impact on the decision-making process of young professionals regarding purchases. The target population comprised young professionals in the Philippines who actively engaged with TikTok and were potential consumers influenced by Filipino TikTok content creators. Quantitative data collection followed a structured approach, primarily through online survey questionnaires designed to measure variables and gather relevant information. Surveys, a proven effective tool for data collection (Fox et al., 2007), were employed consistently throughout the study to gain insights into the influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals. The questionnaires were crafted with clear, relevant, and close-ended questions to ensure effective data gathering.

Population and Sampling

The researchers opted for a sample size of 190 respondents, considering that geographical boundaries weren't relevant to the study. They relied on the assertion that this sample size would provide consistent results, as the sample size doesn't significantly alter for populations larger than or around 200 respondents (Hazra & Gogtay, 2016). Purposive or judgmental sampling was employed for efficiency, aiming to swiftly eliminate respondents who didn't meet the study's criteria.

Instrumentations

The study employed self-constructed survey questionnaires, offering a flexible and rapid research approach to explore environmental, behavioral, and personal influences. The initial section of the questionnaire focused on collecting demographic data from respondents. The subsequent part enabled respondents to correlate the level of influence on the purchasing behavior of young professionals with their personal, environmental, and behavioral influences. Finally, the third section evaluated the impact of Filipino TikTok influencers' level of influence on the purchasing behavior of young professionals.

Data Collection

The data collection process involved self-administered survey questionnaires, developed specifically for the research and approved for posting on Google Forms. Utilizing purposive or judgmental sampling, the researchers leveraged social networking sites and social media platforms, primarily Facebook and Facebook Messenger, to distribute the surveys to eligible participants based on set criteria. Consent was obtained from participants, ensuring confidentiality and avoiding leading or coercive questions, while adhering to ethical standards throughout the

procedure. The data collection spanned two weeks, after which the surveys were taken down. Researchers collected, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the responses upon completion of the data collection period.

Data Analysis

The researchers employed statistical tools to ensure the precise interpretation of the gathered data. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and mean scores, were applied to delineate the socio-demographic traits and purchasing behavior of the participants. Furthermore, inferential statistics such as correlation analysis were utilized to examine the influence of the independent variable, Filipino TikTok influencers, on the dependent variable, which is the buying behavior of young professionals (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014).

Ethical Consideration

Before administering the survey, the researchers secured full consent from respondents through Google Forms. Privacy protection measures were implemented to safeguard the confidentiality of participants, including the use of pseudonyms like "Young Professional" or "YP 1, 2," as necessary. The study refrained from any deception or exaggeration regarding its intentions and objectives, as well as avoiding misleading presentation of primary data results to prevent bias. Communication regarding the research was conducted with honesty and transparency, ensuring clarity and accuracy throughout the process.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings of a study examining the impact of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals. The aim was to comprehend the influence of these influencers and provide recommendations for business utilization and future research. Data were collected through online surveys administered to random respondents, with privacy protected through the use of pseudonyms. Analysis and presentation of the data were conducted using tables, illustrating the influencers' impact on the cognitive factors of young professionals. Additionally, the study explored influencers' influence on purchasing behavior based on various profile variables such as gender, education level, occupation, income, daily TikTok usage, and purchase history.

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents according to Gender

Gender	f	%
Male	70	36.84
Female	120	63.16
Total	190	100.00

Table 1 presents the tabulated data of respondents' profiles categorized by gender. Survey results indicate that 36.84% of respondents were young male professionals, while the majority, constituting 63.16% of the total sample, and were young female professionals. This aligns with findings from Krasnova et al. (2017), suggesting that females tend to use social media more than males, actively fostering social relationships and engaging in activities like commenting on posts and recommending products and services to others.

Table 2

Profile of the Respondents according to Level of Education

Level of Education	F	%
HS Grad	30	15.79
Assoc Degree	1	0.53
College Undergrad	37	19.47
College Grad	99	52.10
Master's	23	12.11
Total	190	100.00

Table 2 displays the computed and tabulated data of respondents' profiles categorized by their level of education. Among the respondents, 12.11% hold master's degrees, 15.79% are high school graduates, 19.47% are college undergraduates, and the majority, comprising 52.10%, are college graduates. This varied educational distribution sets the stage for exploring the influence of education on the consumer behavior of young professionals. Education appears to impact consumer behavior, as higher-educated individuals are noted for their analytical and well-informed decision-making, engaging in thorough research and comparisons (Chan, 2022). Moreover, more educated consumers tend to deliberate carefully before making purchases, emphasizing thoughtful consideration (Pratap, 2017).

Table 3

Profile of the Respondents according to Occupation

Occupation	F	%
Business Professional	18	9.47
Business Owner	18	9.47
Medical	11	5.79
Government Service	42	22.11
Clerical	6	3.16
Educator	17	8.95
Manager	7	3.68
Customer Service	10	5.26
Sales	25	13.16
Laborer	12	6.32
Technical/Engineering	17	8.95
Social Services	1	0.53
Hospitality	4	2.11
Transportation	2	1.05
Total	190	100.00

Table 3 illustrates the computed and tabulated data of respondents' profiles categorized by occupation. Notably, social services professionals were the least represented at 0.53%, while hospitality and transportation workers comprised 2.11% and 1.05%, respectively. Clerical and management professionals accounted for 3.16% and 3.68%, respectively, while customer service professionals constituted 5.26% of the total sample. Laborers/medical employees

and technology/engineering professionals each comprised 6.32% and 8.95% of respondents, respectively. Educators represented 8.95% of respondents, with business professionals and business owners equally represented at 9.47% each. Sales professionals accounted for 13.16% of respondents, while the majority were government employees, comprising 22.11% of the total sample. Studies by Liu et al. (2022) and Anagha et al. (2020) highlight the significance of these demographic profiles, suggesting that professional competence may influence the purchasing behavior of young professionals, who may prioritize purchases related to their profession or current occupation.

Table 4

Profile of the Respondents according to Income

Income	f	%
Less than 9,100	56	29.47
9,100-18,200	65	34.21
18,200-36,400	43	22.63
36,400-63,700	20	10.53
63,700-109,200	5	2.63
109,200-182,000	0	0.00
182,000 above	1	0.53
Total	190	100.00

Table 4 outlines the computed and tabulated data of respondents' profiles categorized by income. Notably, 10.53% of respondents fall within the Php 36,400 to 63,700 monthly family income range, categorized as the middle middle-income class. Conversely, those earning Php 182,000 and above comprise the smallest percentage of the sample at 0.53%. A substantial portion, approximately 22.63%, earn Php 18,200 to 36,400, classified as the lower middle-income class, while 29.47% earn less than Php 9,100, indicating they belong to the poor cluster. The majority, comprising 34.21% of respondents, fall into the low-income class. The income range of Php 9,100 to 18,200 represents the low-income class (but not poor), with respondents in this range comprising the largest portion of the sample at 34.21%. Income significantly influences the purchasing behavior of young professionals, directly impacting their purchasing decisions. Lower-income individuals are more likely to prioritize necessities due to budget constraints, whereas higher-income individuals tend to purchase more expensive products (Pratap, 2017).

Table 5

Profile of the Respondents according to Hours spent daily on TikTok

Hours Spent Daily on TikTok	F	%
1-3 hours	151	79.47
4-6 hours	33	17.37
7 hours or more	6	3.16
Total	190	100.00

Table 5 presents the computed and tabulated data of respondents' profiles categorized by their daily TikTok usage hours. The smallest group, comprising 3.16% of respondents, spent seven hours or more using the application.

Those who used TikTok for four to six hours accounted for 17.37% of the total sample. The majority, comprising 79.47% of respondents, reported using TikTok for one to three hours daily.

Although no specific studies support the direct impact of daily TikTok usage on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, it can be inferred that increased time spent on TikTok may expose individuals to influencer marketing campaigns. TikTok's algorithm is known for detecting user interests and frequently showing relevant content, contributing to trends like #TikTokMadeMeBuyIt. Leeuwen (2023) identified six distinct mechanisms employed by social media platforms, including TikTok, to prolong user engagement, potentially leading to increased exposure to promotional content and a higher likelihood of sales conversion for companies.

Table 6

Profile of the Respondents according to Product discoveries and purchases in TikTok

No. of Times Purchased in TikTok	f	%
1-3 times	151	79.47
4-6 times	34	17.89
7-9 times	4	2.11
10 times	1	0.53
Total	190	100.00

Table 6 displays the computed and tabulated data of respondents' profiles categorized by their product discoveries and purchase history using the application. The smallest percentage of respondents, at 0.53%, reported making purchases 10 times or more in a month. Additionally, 2.11% and 17.89% of the sample reported purchasing from TikTok four to six times and seven to nine times a month, respectively. The majority of respondents (79.47%) reported purchasing products one to three times a month. Research by Etrata et al. (2022) suggests that increased audience engagement correlates with a higher intention to purchase. Thus, it can be inferred that the longer consumers are engaged in the pre-purchase environment, the more likely they are to make a purchase.

Table 7

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals in terms of Environmental Factor

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. Filipino TikTok influencers have influenced my purchasing decisions.	3.18	Somewhat Influential	3
2. I am more likely to purchase products or services recommended by Filipino TikTok influencers.	3.01	Somewhat Influential	9
3. I have purchased products/services recommended by TikTok influencers.	3.17	Somewhat Influential	4
4. I am more likely to consider a product/service if it is recommended by TikTok influencers.	3.05	Somewhat Influential	8
5. I am more swayed to purchase a product after reading positive comments in a Filipino TikTok influencer's post or endorsement of a product	3.25	Somewhat Influential	1

6. I believe that TikTok influencers provide reliable information about products/services.	3.07	Somewhat Influential	7
7. Filipino TikTok influencers determine what’s trending among my peers.	3.23	Somewhat Influential	2
8. I believe the credibility and authenticity of the influencer is a significant factor in my purchasing behavior.	3.11	Somewhat Influential	6
9. My family has made purchases in the past that they didn't regret, so when they recommend products, I tend to trust their judgment.	3.12	Somewhat Influential	5
Composite Mean	3.13	Somewhat Influential	

Table 7 displays computed and tabulated data regarding the influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, specifically focusing on environmental factors. The indicators within this category all garnered a somewhat influential level of influence.

Rankings 9 and 8 suggest that respondents are more likely to consider and purchase products or services recommended by Filipino TikTok influencers, with weighted means (WM) of 3.01 and 3.05, respectively. These indicators highlight the importance of influencer recommendations in the pre-purchase environment.

Under rank 7, respondents believe that TikTok influencers provide reliable information about products or services, with a WM of 3.07, reflecting trust in influencer content.

The credibility and authenticity of Filipino TikTok influencers are considered significant factors in purchasing behavior, ranking 6th with a WM of 3.11. Influencers offer a level of trust not easily attained through traditional advertising.

Respondents trust their families' product recommendations, ranking 5th with a WM of 3.12, indicating the influence of social norms on purchasing behavior.

Purchasing products or services recommended by TikTok influencers is ranked 4th with a WM of 3.17, showing the impact of peer influence on purchasing decisions.

Filipino TikTok influencers are perceived to determine trends among peers and influence purchasing decisions, ranking 3rd and 2nd with WMs of 3.18 and 3.23, respectively. This underscores the influence of social groups on purchasing behavior.

Respondents are more swayed to purchase products after reading positive comments in a TikTok influencer's post, ranking 1st with a WM of 3.25. This aligns with the influence of influencer endorsements on consumer behavior.

Overall, the endorsement of products by Filipino TikTok influencers adds a cultural and social dimension, influencing consumer preferences and purchasing behavior among young professionals.

Table 8

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals in terms of Personal Factors

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. The purchasing decisions of my peers are often influenced by Filipino TikTok influencers which in turn affect my choices.	2.98	Somewhat Influential	9
2. My usual purchases including the brands that I like align with my personal goals and values.	3.13	Somewhat Influential	3
3. Many of my purchasing choices are driven by my innate desire to acquire them.	3.15	Somewhat Influential	2
4. I have trust in the recommendations made by Filipino TikTok influencers.	3.01	Somewhat Influential	7
5. I consider the information provided by Filipino TikTok influencers when making purchasing decisions.	3.02	Somewhat Influential	6
6. I believe in Filipino TikTok influencers especially if they don't trust in a specific product.	3.00	Somewhat Influential	8
7. The usage of specific products demonstrated by Filipino TikTok influencers (e.g., cooking, fashion, makeup, fitness) influenced my interest in acquiring said products.	3.08	Somewhat Influential	5
8. Filipino TikTok influencers have introduced me to new brands or products.	3.15	Somewhat Influential	1
9. I often come across product or service recommendations from Filipino TikTok influencers.	3.08	Somewhat Influential	4
Composite Mean	3.06	Somewhat Influential	

Table 8 presents computed and tabulated data on the level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals concerning personal factors. All indicators within this category garnered a somewhat influential level of influence.

The purchasing decisions of peers influenced by TikTok influencers affect respondents' choices, with a weighted mean (WM) of 2.98. This aligns with the Social Cognitive Theory, emphasizing the significant role influencers play in shaping consumer behavior through social influence.

Respondents consider information provided by influencers, especially when they distrust a specific product, with a WM of 3.00. This indicates the importance of influencers in conveying credible information to consumers.

Trust in the recommendations of Filipino TikTok influencers is significant, with a WM of 3.01. This trust establishes a symbiotic dynamic between influencers and brands, influencing purchasing decisions.

Exposure to products or services endorsed by influencers influences respondents' interest in acquiring those products, with WMs of 3.08. This reflects the importance of meaningful connections with brands and positive emotional responses from consumers leading to purchases.

Respondents' usual purchases align with their personal goals and values, with a WM of 3.13. This underscores the individuality of consumers and how their characteristics, beliefs, and attitudes affect their purchasing decisions.

Introduction to new brands or products by Filipino TikTok influencers drives purchases, with WMs of 3.15. This highlights the effectiveness of influencer marketing in brand awareness and introducing products to consumers.

Overall, Filipino TikTok influencers play a significant role in shaping the purchasing behavior of young professionals through personal factors, influencing choices based on social influence, trust, credibility, alignment with personal values, and exposure to new brands or products.

Table 9

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals in terms of Behavioral Factors

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. The affirmation of Filipino TikTok influencers as regards my purchases make my purchases worth it.	3.07	Somewhat Influential	7
2. I have adopted new buying habits based on the recommendations of Filipino TikTok influencers.	2.99	Somewhat Influential	8
3. I turn to Filipino TikTok influencers after buying a product to verify their reviews and opinions about it.	3.08	Somewhat Influential	6
4. I have followed trends or practices popularized by Filipino TikTok influencers in my purchasing behavior.	2.97	Somewhat Influential	9
5. I have confidence in my ability to gather relevant information about a certain product and select from them.	3.29	Somewhat Influential	1
6. Filipino TikTok influencers have helped me make informed purchasing decisions.	3.12	Somewhat Influential	4
7. I believe that I can replicate the positive experiences with products or services recommended by Filipino TikTok influencers.	3.18	Somewhat Influential	3
8. When an expert Filipino TikTok influencer (a make-up artist for a make-up product, or an esthetician for a skin care product) recommends the product that I've purchased, I recommend the same product to my peers as well.	3.11	Somewhat Influential	5
9. I know if a Filipino TikTok influencer's post is sponsored and is aimed to manipulate consumers, that's why I became more selective in choosing the influencers I follow on the said platform.	3.25	Somewhat Influential	2
Composite Mean	3.12	Somewhat Influential	

Table 9 presents computed and tabulated data on the level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals in terms of behavioral factors. All indicators within this category garnered a somewhat influential level of influence.

Respondents have followed trends or practices popularized by Filipino TikTok influencers in their purchasing behavior, with a weighted mean (WM) of 2.97. This suggests that influencers significantly shape consumer choices by influencing the adoption of popular trends and practices.

Adopting new buying habits influenced by Filipino TikTok influencers is significant, with a WM of 2.99. Individuals rely on influencers for guidance in navigating purchasing decisions, reflecting the impact of influencers on shopping habits and buying patterns.

Turning to Filipino TikTok influencers after buying a product to verify their reviews and opinions about it is common, with a WM of 3.08. This reflects the modern consumer's need for reassurance and validation before making purchase decisions.

Influencers help respondents make informed decisions, with a WM of 3.12, and allow them to recommend the same products to their peers, with a WM of 3.11. This underscores the importance of influencers in post-purchase behavior and the influence of product reviews on subsequent purchasing decisions.

Respondents believe they can replicate the positive experiences of influencers with products they recommend, with a WM of 3.18. Emotional engagement with influencer content influences purchase intentions, particularly among Generation Z consumers.

Awareness of sponsored influencer posts and selectivity in choosing whom to follow on TikTok are evident, with a WM of 3.25. Consumers with higher education levels tend to approach decision-making with greater scrutiny and analysis.

Confidence in their abilities to gather relevant information about a product and select from it is high, with a WM of 3.29. Consumers rely on platforms like TikTok for information gathering and market trends analysis throughout the purchase decision-making process.

Overall, Filipino TikTok influencers play a significant role in shaping the purchasing behavior of young professionals through behavioral factors, influencing trends adoption, buying habits, information verification, post-purchase behavior, and consumer confidence in decision-making.

Table 10

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to profile variables

Profile	df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
Gender	199	0.959	0.385	Not Significant	Accept
Education	199	8.999	0.000	Significant	Reject
Occupation	199	1.587	0.076	Not Significant	Accept
Income	199	1.091	0.369	Not Significant	Accept
Daily Spent in TikTok	199	0.887	0.414	Not Significant	Accept
No. of TikTok purchases in a month	199	0.494	0.687	Not Significant	Accept

Reject Ho if p- value \leq 0.05

Table 10 showed the significant difference between the levels of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to profile variables: gender, education, occupation, income, daily spent in TikTok, and number of times they have purchased in TikTok.

Table 11

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to education

Profile	df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
Education	199	8.999	0.000	Significant	Reject

Reject Ho if p- value ≤ 0.05

The analysis indicates that education significantly influences the level of influence Filipino TikTok influencers have on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, as evidenced by a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a notable difference in assessments based on educational attainment. Consumers with higher education levels, as suggested by Chan (2022), are inclined to conduct more research and base decisions on findings, seeking online validation for purchases. However, it's worth noting that individuals with lower formal education levels can also develop sophisticated consumer attitudes through practical experiences and exposure to various information sources, as emphasized by Jawahar and Tamizjyothi (2013).

Table 12

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to number of TikTok purchases in a month

Profile	Df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
No. of TikTok purchases in a month	199	0.494	0.687	Not Significant	Accept

Reject Ho if p- value ≤ 0.05

Likewise, the number of purchases in a month on TikTok (df = 199, F = 0.494) has a p-value of $0.687 > 0.05$, which is indicative that the assessments made were not significant. The null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference between the levels of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to the number of TikTok purchases in a month. This result is in consonance with the fact that there are no studies or journals that support the fact that there is a significant difference between the levels of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to the number of TikTok purchases in a month.

Table 13

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to time spent daily on TikTok

Profile	df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
Daily Spent in TikTok	199	0.887	0.414	Not Significant	Accept

Reject Ho if p- value ≤ 0.05

The analysis found that the hours spent daily on TikTok did not significantly influence the level of influence Filipino TikTok influencers had on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, as indicated by a p-value of 0.414 > 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting no notable difference in assessments based on daily TikTok usage. Given that the majority of respondents spent one to three hours daily on TikTok, assumptions about increased purchases with longer usage may not hold true. Consequently, findings from studies by Leeuwen (2023), Leykin et al. (2014), and Araujo et al. (2022), which link audience engagement to purchase decisions, may not apply directly. As a result, it's challenging to determine a significant difference in the level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals based on daily TikTok usage.

Table 14

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to income

Profile	df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
Income	199	1.091	0.369	Not Significant	Accept

Reject Ho if p- value ≤ 0.05

The analysis revealed that income did not significantly affect the level of influence Filipino TikTok influencers had on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, with a p-value of 0.369 > 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no substantial difference in assessments based on income levels. However, it's worth noting that the closed-ended nature of the survey questions limits exploration into the reasons behind young professionals' purchasing considerations.

Table 15

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to occupation

Profile	Df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
Occupation	199	1.587	0.076	Not Significant	Accept

Reject Ho if p- value ≤ 0.05

The analysis indicated that occupation did not significantly impact the level of influence Filipino TikTok influencers had on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, with a p-value of $0.076 > 0.05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting no notable difference in assessments based on occupation. Similarly, the closed-ended nature of the survey questions limited exploration into the potential reasons behind young professionals' purchasing considerations in relation to their occupation.

Table 16

The level of influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals when grouped according to gender

Profile	Df	F	p- value	Description	Decision on Ho
Gender	199	0.959	0.385	Not Significant	Accept

Reject Ho if p- value ≤ 0.05

The analysis found that gender did not significantly influence the level of influence Filipino TikTok influencers had on the purchasing behavior of young professionals, with a p-value of $0.3895 > 0.05$. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no substantial difference in assessments based on gender. Additionally, the closed-ended nature of the survey questions limited the exploration of the influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals.

Table 17

Advocacy Plan

Components	Description
Focus of Advocacy Plan	Leverage Filipino TikTok influencers to positively influence the purchasing behavior of young professionals
Strategies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initiate workshops for marketers to enhance their content creation skills and promote responsible marketing practices 2. Launch consumer education campaigns to raise awareness among young professionals about the impact of influencer marketing on their purchasing decisions
Coordination	Coordinate with the local Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) to collaborate on the initiatives
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of influencers participating in workshops • Number of young professionals engaging in workshops • Success of consumer education campaigns in reaching the target audience
Timeline	Twelve (12) months, including workshops, consumer education campaigns, collaborative campaigns, and advocacy events

Evaluation	Regular evaluations and adjustments planned to ensure continuous improvement
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The advocacy plan aims to utilize Filipino TikTok influencers to positively shape the purchasing behavior of young professionals. It involves organizing workshops for marketers to improve content creation skills and promote responsible marketing. Concurrently, consumer education campaigns will be launched to raise awareness among young professionals about influencer marketing's impact. Collaboration with the local Department of Trade and Industry will be sought. Key performance indicators include tracking engagement in workshops and the success of consumer education campaigns. The initiative spans twelve months and includes collaborative campaigns and advocacy events. Regular evaluations are planned to ensure continuous improvement.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from the study shed light on various aspects of the influence of Filipino TikTok influencers on the purchasing behavior of young professionals. The findings suggest a strong correlation between education levels and decision-making processes, with higher education leading to more informed choices and reliance on online resources for purchase assurance. Filipino TikTok influencers exert significant influence on young professionals, particularly in terms of environmental, personal, and behavioral factors, as evidenced by the propensity of respondents to make purchases after encountering influencer endorsements.

Despite demographic differences such as gender, occupation, income, time spent on TikTok, and frequency of purchases not significantly impacting influencer influence, educational attainment emerges as the most influential factor. Interestingly, while there are no significant differences in influencer impact based on various demographic factors such as gender, income, occupation, time spent on TikTok, and frequency of purchases, education plays a pivotal role in shaping consumer attitudes and behaviors. Higher education levels are linked to enhanced cognitive abilities, suggesting that educated young professionals are more likely to possess improved intuition and analytical skills, enabling them to make more informed purchasing decisions. These conclusions underscore the importance of education in empowering consumers to make informed decisions and navigate influencer marketing landscapes effectively.

Recommendations

The recommendations drawn from the study's findings offer valuable insights for marketing students, researchers, and educational institutions. Firstly, the study suggests that marketing professionals should conduct further research to understand the distinct preferences, motivations, and decision-making processes of male demographics, thereby enabling more targeted marketing strategies. Continuous learning initiatives are recommended for young professionals, emphasizing the importance of ongoing education to enhance cognitive skills and personal growth, which can benefit both individuals and organizations. Targeted market research is advised to explore the purchasing behavior of young professionals in government roles, offering opportunities for tailored marketing approaches. Furthermore, future research should delve into the effectiveness of influencer marketing across different

income brackets and demographic groups, providing insights for content creators and marketing teams to optimize their strategies.

Collaboration between local governments and Filipino TikTok influencers is encouraged, leveraging their influence to effectively reach and engage young professionals. Moreover, conducting in-depth studies by interdisciplinary teams can yield a deeper understanding of the psychological and behavioral factors influencing purchasing decisions, informing businesses on how to tailor content and improve online platforms to meet consumer needs effectively. Overall, these recommendations underscore the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, continuous learning, and targeted research in enhancing marketing strategies and consumer engagement, ultimately benefiting both academic and practical domains within the field of marketing.

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